

Knowledge on Prelacteal Feeding Among Primi Antenatal Mothers and Associated Factors of Prelacteal Feeding During Immediate Postnatal Period of Mothers Admitted in Tertiary Care Hospitals of Gangtok, East Sikkim

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Abstract

Background: Breastfeeding is crucial for the health and survival of infants, but the introduction of Prelacteal feeds hinders exclusive breastfeeding. This study aimed to assess knowledge on the harmful effects of Prelacteal feeding, the importance of breastfeeding, identify associated factors, and explore demographic variables. **Method:** A descriptive study was conducted with 290 primi antenatal mothers admitted in tertiary care hospital of Gangtok, East Sikkim. **Results:** It showed that 72.1% of mothers had average knowledge, 20.7% had good knowledge, and 7.2% had poor knowledge regarding Prelacteal feeding. Only 29.3% of mothers administered Prelacteal feeds, primarily formula feed (52.9%). Factors influencing the administration of Prelacteal feeds included NICU admission (37.6%), cultural beliefs (21.2%), and peer advice (16.5%). Knowledge on harmful effects and the importance of breastfeeding were significantly associated with health education ($p < 0.05$). Age, occupation, type of family, residency, monthly income, and health education regarding newborn feeding were also associated with the factors influencing Prelacteal feeding ($p < 0.05$). **Conclusion:** The study concludes that despite knowledge, cultural and other factors influence the administration of Prelacteal feeding. Adequate health education and minimizing the use of breastmilk substitutes are recommended to promote breastfeeding practices.

Keywords Prelacteal Feeding, Knowledge, Associated Factor, Antenatal Mothers, Immediate Postnatal Mothers.

Introduction

Breastfeeding is a powerful way to promote the health and survival of infants. It starts within an hour after birth, shielding newborns from infections and reducing mortality rates. [1] Breastfeeding is unmatched in providing essential nutrition for newborns, supporting their healthy growth and development. It is not only vital for infants but also holds significant implications for maternal health and the reproductive process. [2] Breastfeeding aids in uterine involution through oxytocin release, while providing immunological advantages through maternal antibodies, especially secretory immunoglobulin A (IgA), protecting the infant's gut from harmful bacteria. Breast milk contains essential proteins, lactose, fats, and delivers amino acids from the mother's blood. It is also a source of omega-3 fatty acids crucial for early brain development. [3] WHO and UNICEF advise initiating breastfeeding within the first hour after birth, exclusively breastfeeding for six months, and continuing for two years or more alongside appropriate complementary feeding starting at six months. [4]

Aim of study

1. Assess the level of knowledge on Prelacteal feeding among primi antenatal mothers admitted in tertiary care hospitals of Gangtok, East Sikkim.
2. Determine association between knowledge on Prelacteal feeding among primi antenatal mother with selected demographic variables admitted in tertiary care hospitals of Gangtok, East Sikkim.

3. Identify associated factor of prelacteal feeding among immediate postnatal mother admitted in tertiary care hospitals of Gangtok, East Sikkim.
4. Find an association of associated factor of prelacteal feeding among immediate postnatal mothers with selected demographic variables.

Review of Literature

Colostrum provides vital immune protection and prepares the infant's gut for nutrient absorption. Only colostrum should be given to newborns initially. Prelacteal feeds, are foods and fluids given to a newborn before breastfeeding begins. Prelacteal feeds, given before breastfeeding initiation and colostrum intake, raise the risk of diarrhoea, infections, and allergies in newborns. These feeds satisfy hunger and thirst, reducing interest in breastfeeding and hampering breast milk production.[5] Across different countries, practices like discarding colostrum or introducing liquids and non-breastmilk food to newborns by doctors or family members vary. These practices may delay crucial mother-newborn interaction. Introduction of non-breastmilk substances is prevalent in several regions, often driven by cultural norms, family traditions, or hospital regulations without scientific basis.[6]

Prelacteal feeding negatively impacts exclusive breastfeeding. When a child receives prelacteal feed, they are not considered exclusively breastfed.[7]

As the primary carriers of traditions, women play a crucial role in cultural heritage. Feeding practices, including breastfeeding, hold great importance in preserving these traditions. Women who come from families without a history of nursing may be eager to be the first to initiate breastfeeding. Conversely, some cultures believe colostrum is not suitable for newborns and prefer to wait until mature milk is present, typically around three days after birth.[8]

Eastern and Southern Africa exhibit the highest rate (65%) of breastfeeding within the first hour after birth, while East Asia and the Pacific have the lowest rate (32%). In India, prelacteal feeds such as honey, sugar water, ghee, or herbal preparations are commonly given, often influenced by specific family, caste, or religious practices.[9]

Main Text**Hypothesis**

H1: There is a significant association between knowledge on prelacteal feeding with selected demographic variables among the mothers admitted to tertiary care hospital of Gangtok, East Sikkim.

H2: There is a significant association between associated factor of prelacteal feeding with selected demographic variables among the mothers admitted to tertiary care hospitals of Gangtok, East Sikkim.

Methodology

Non-experimental Quantitative approach with descriptive survey design was used to determine the knowledge on harmful effect of prelacteal feeding and importance of breastfeeding among primi antenatal mothers and associated factors of prelacteal feeding during immediate postnatal period. The study was conducted in tertiary care hospitals of Gangtok, East Sikkim i.e Central Referral Hospital and STNM Hospital.

Probability simple random sampling technique was used to select the sample. 290 Primi antenatal mothers and the same mother immediately after delivery admitted in tertiary care hospitals of Gangtok, East Sikkim who were willing to participate and could understand English, Nepali or Hindi were selected.

The data was collected through self- reported technique. Two structured tools were used to assess the knowledge and associated factor of Prelacteal feeding among primi antenatal and immediate postnatal mother.

Tool 1 consists of demographic proforma, and structured knowledge questionnaire and tool II consist of Structed questionnaire to determine the associated factor of prelacteal feeding.

Result and Discussion

Table1: Frequency and percentage distribution of demographic variables.

N=290

S. No	Demographic Variables	f	%
1	Age in years		
	a. Less than 20 years	24	8.3
	b. 21-25 years	87	30
	c. 26-30 years	117	40.3
	d. More than 31 years	62	21.4
2	Religion		
	a. Hindu	152	52.4
	b. Buddhist	85	29.3
	c. Muslim	8	2.8
	d. Christian	44	15.2
	e. Others (Shadu)	1	0.3
3	Educational status		
	a. No formal education	22	7.6
	b. Primary	96	33.1
	c. Secondary	108	37.2
	d. Graduate	42	14.5
	e. Postgraduate	20	6.9
	f. PhD	2	0.7
4	Husbands' Educational status		
	a. No formal education	17	5.9
	b. Primary	112	38.6
	c. Secondary	109	37.6
	d. Graduate	32	11
	e. Postgraduate	18	6.2
	f. PhD	2	0.7
5	Occupational status		
	a. Professional	18	6.2
	b. Semi professional	35	12.1
	c. Daily wage worker	20	6.9
	d. Self employed	17	5.9
	e. Housewife	200	69
6	Monthly family income		
	a. Less than 15,000	173	59.7
	b. 16,000-45,000	84	29
	c. 46,000-75,000	22	7.6
	d. More than 75,000	11	3.8
7	Type of family		
	a. Joint family	121	41.7
	b. Nuclear family	160	55.2
	c. Single parent	9	3.1
8	Support person available		
	a. Yes	180	62.1
	b. No	110	37.9
	If yes		
	a. Friend	2	0.7
	b. In-laws	61	21
	c. Mother	69	23.8
d. Sister	48	16.6	
9	Residency		
	a. Urban	96	33.1
	b. Rural	194	66.9
10	Duration of pregnancy		
	a. 8 months	19	6.6
	b. 9 months	271	93.4
11	ANC follow up till date		
	a. Only one time	10	3.4
	b. Twice	13	4.5
	c. Three times	29	10
	d. More than 3 times	238	82.1
12	Antenatal counseling received		
	a. Yes	151	52.1
	b. No	139	47.9
13	Any health education regarding new-born feeding?		
	a. Yes	143	49.3
	b. No	147	50.7
13.1	Who gave you education?		
	a. Health care professionals	99	69.3
	b. Peer group	24	16.7
	c. Mass media	9	6.3
	d. Internet	11	7.7

Table 2: Distribution of level of knowledge on Prelacteal feeding among primi antenatal mothers.

N=290

Knowledge	f	%	Score Range	Median	Mean	SD	Mean %
Poor knowledge	21	7.2	3-16	10	9.57	2.627	59.8 %
Average knowledge	209	72.1					
Good knowledge	60	20.7					

Description of associated factor of Prolactal feeding.

N=290

Fig 2: Frequency Percentage distribution of mode of delivery of mother

N=290

Fig 3: Frequency Percentage distribution of whether Prolactal feed was administered to the new-born.

N=290, n=85

Fig 4: Frequency Percentage distribution of Individuals who administered Prelacteal feed to the newborn.

n=85

Fig 5: Frequency Percentage distribution of the type of feed administered to the newborn.

n=85

Fig 6: Frequency Percentage distribution of factors influencing Prelacteal feed

Table 3. Association between knowledge on Prelacteal feeding among primi antenatal mother with selected demographic variables.

N=290

Demographic Variables	Knowledge			χ ² value	df	p value
	Poor	Average	Good			
1. Age in years						
a. Less than 20 years	1	17	6	1.679	6	0.947 ^{NS}
b. 21-25 years	8	60	19			
c. 26-30 years	7	87	23			
d. More than 31 years	5	45	12			
2. Religion						
a. Hindu	11	109	32	3.195	8	0.922 ^{NS}
b. Buddhist	7	64	14			
c. Muslim	0	6	2			
d. Christian	3	29	12			
e. Others	0	1	0			
3. Educational status						
a. No formal education	0	18	4	15.35	10	0.120 ^{NS}
b. Primary	4	71	21			
c. Secondary	11	77	20			
d. Graduate	4	31	7			
e. Postgraduate	1	12	7			
f. PhD	1	0	1			
4. Husbands' Educational status						
a. No formal education	0	12	5	15.84	10	0.104 ^{NS}
b. Primary	7	84	21			
c. Secondary	8	81	20			
d. Graduate	4	22	6			
e. Postgraduate	1	9	8			
f. PhD	1	1	0			
5. Occupational status						
a. Professional	2	10	6	7.199	8	0.515 ^{NS}
b. Semi professional	2	26	7			
c. Daily wage worker	1	18	1			
d. Self employed.	1	14	2			
e. Housewife	15	141	44			
6. Monthly family income						
a. Less than 15,000	11	127	35	8.204	6	0.224 ^{NS}
b. 16,000-45,000	8	63	13			
c. 46,000-75,000	1	14	7			
d. More than 75,000	1	5	5			
7. Type of family						
a. Joint family	7	82	32	4.717	4	0.318 ^{NS}
b. Nuclear family	13	120	27			
c. Single parent	1	7	1			
8. Support person available						
a. Yes	10	130	40	2.403	2	0.301 ^{NS}
b. No	11	79	20			
9. Residency						
a. Urban	8	70	18	0.512	2	0.774 ^{NS}
b. Rural	13	139	42			
10. Duration of pregnancy						
a. 8 months	4	12	3	5.816	2	0.055 ^{NS}
b. 9 months	17	197	57			
11. ANC follow up till date						
a. Only one time	1	7	2	4.102	6	0.663 ^{NS}
b. Twice	2	9	2			
c. Three times	4	20	5			
d. More than 3 times	14	173	51			
12. Antenatal counseling received						
a. Yes	7	116	28	4.642	2	0.098 ^{NS}
b. No	14	93	32			
13. Any health education regarding new-born feeding?						
a. Yes	6	112	25	6.546	2	0.038*
b. No	15	97	35			

*p value < 0.05 level of significance NS-Non-Significant

Table 3 showed that health education regarding new-born feeding was found to have significant association at p<0.05 level with knowledge on Pre-lacteal feeding among Primi antenatal mother.

Table 4. Association between mode of delivery among immediate postnatal mothers with selected demographic variables.

N=290

Demographic Variables	Mode of delivery		χ^2 value	df	p value
	Vaginal delivery	Caesarean section			
1. Age in years					
a. Less than 20 years	14	10	10.05	3	0.018*
b. 21-25 years	39	48			
c. 26-30 years	35	82			
d. More than 31 years	20	42			
2. Religion					
a. Hindu	60	92	9.190	4	0.057 ^{NS}
b. Buddhist	35	50			
c. Muslim	0	8			
d. Christian	12	32			
e. Others	1	0			
3. Educational status					
a. No formal education	11	11	4.329	5	0.503 ^{NS}
b. Primary	37	59			
c. Secondary	40	68			
d. Graduate	15	27			
e. Postgraduate	4	16			
f. PhD	1	1			
4. Husbands' educational status					
a. No formal education	8	9	2.663	5	0.752 ^{NS}
b. Primary	40	72			
c. Secondary	44	65			
d. Graduate	9	23			
e. Postgraduate	6	12			
f. PhD	1	1			
5. Occupational status					
a. Professional	8	10	21.56	4	0.001*
b. Semi professional	25	10			
c. Daily wage worker	5	15			
d. Self employed	6	11			
e. Housewife	64	136			
6. Monthly family income					
a. Less than 15,000	68	105	2.376	3	0.498 ^{NS}
b. 16,000-45,000	26	58			
c. 46,000-75,000	10	12			
d. More than 75,000	4	7			
7. Type of family					
a. Joint family	62	59	18.61	2	0.001*
b. Nuclear family	42	118			
c. Single parent	4	5			
8. Support person available					
a. Yes	68	112	0.058	1	0.809 ^{NS}
b. No	40	70			
9. Residency					
a. Urban	56	40	27.31	1	0.001*
b. Rural	52	142			
10. Duration of pregnancy					
a. 8 months	8	11	0.206	1	0.650 ^{NS}
b. 9 months	100	171			
11. ANC follow up till date					
a. Only one time	4	6	0.274	3	0.965 ^{NS}
b. Twice	4	9			
c. Three times	11	18			
d. More than 3 times	89	149			
12. Antenatal counseling received					
a. Yes	56	95	0.003	1	0.955 ^{NS}
b. No	52	87			
13. Any health education regarding new-born feeding?					
a. Yes	53	90	0.004	1	0.951 ^{NS}
b. No	55	92			

*p value < 0.05 level of significance NS-Non-Significant

Table 4. depicts that age, occupational status, type of family and residency was found to have significant association at $p < 0.05$ level with mode of delivery of immediate postnatal mothers.

Table 5. Association between Prelacteal feed administered to newborn among immediate postnatal mothers with selected demographic variables.

N=290

Demographic Variables	Prelacteal feed to your newborn		χ^2 -value	df	p value
	Yes	No			
1. Age in years					
a. Less than 20 years	6	18	9.3.15	3	0.025 ^{NS}
b. 21-25 years	25	62			
c. 26-30 years	44	73			
d. More than 31 years	10	52			
2. Religion					
a. Hindu	41	111	7.211	4	0.125 ^{NS}
b. Buddhist	29	56			
c. Muslim	0	8			
d. Christian	14	30			
e. Others	1	0			
3. Educational status					
a. No formal education	10	12	5.010	5	0.415 ^{NS}
b. Primary	26	70			
c. Secondary	31	77			
d. Graduate	14	28			
e. Postgraduate	4	16			
f. PhD	0	2			
4. Husbands' educational status					
a. No formal education	4	13	5.377	5	0.372 ^{NS}
b. Primary	37	75			
c. Secondary	35	74			
d. Graduate	6	26			
e. Postgraduate	3	15			
f. PhD	0	2			
5. Occupational status					
a. Professional	2	16	5.769	4	0.217 ^{NS}
b. Semi professional	9	26			
c. Daily wage worker	9	11			
d. Self employed	6	11			
e. Housewife	59	141			
6. Monthly family income					
a. Less than 15,000	32	141	28.05	3	0.001*
b. 16,000-45,000	45	49			
c. 46,000-75,000	7	15			
d. More than 75,000	1	10			
7. Type of family					
a. Joint family	39	82	1.027	2	0.599 ^{NS}
b. Nuclear family	43	117			
c. Single parent	3	6			
8. Support person available					
a. Yes	55	125	0.355	1	0.551 ^{NS}
b. No	30	80			
9. Residency					
a. Urban	44	52	18.90	1	0.001*
b. Rural	41	153			
10. Duration of pregnancy					
a. 8 months	7	12	0.557	1	0.456 ^{NS}
b. 9 months	78	193			
11. ANC follow up till date					
a. Only one time	4	6	1.738	3	0.629 ^{NS}
b. Twice	5	8			
c. Three times	10	19			
d. More than 3 times	66	172			
12. Antenatal counseling received					
a. Yes	37	114	3.513	1	0.061 ^{NS}
b. No	48	91			
13. Any health education regarding new-born feeding?					
a. Yes	33	110	5.290	1	0.021*
b. No	52	95			

Table 5 depicts that there was a significant association ($p < 0.05$) observed with monthly income, residency, and health education on newborn feeding.

Table 6: Association between who gave the prelacteal feeding among immediate postnatal mothers with selected demographic variables

Text
 Box:

Demographic Variables	Who gave the prelacteal feeding				χ^2 value	df	p value
	Grand Mother	Husband	Your self	Others			
1. Age in years							
a. Less than 20 years	0	0	2	4	13.78	9	0.130 ^{NS}
b. 21-25 years	2	2	2	19			
c. 26-30 years	11	2	3	28			
d. More than 31 years	3	2	0	5			
2. Religion							
a. Hindu	4	5	6	25	14.71	9	0.099 ^{NS}
b. Buddhist	7	1	1	21			
c. Muslim	--	--	--	--			
d. Christian	4	0	0	10			
e. Others	1	0	0	0			
3. Educational status							
a. No formal education	4	0	0	6	15.11	12	0.235 ^{NS}
b. Primary	4	3	1	17			
c. Secondary	6	1	5	21			
d. Graduate	1	1	0	11			
e. Postgraduate	1	1	1	1			
f. PhD	--	--	--	--			
4. Husbands' educational status							
a. No formal education	1	0	0	4	12.80	12	0.383 ^{NS}
b. Primary	9	2	2	21			
c. Secondary	6	2	3	25			
d. Graduate	0	2	1	5			
e. Postgraduate	0	0	1	1			
f. PhD	--	--	--	--			
5. Occupational status							
a. Professional	0	0	0	3	11.50	12	0.486 ^{NS}
b. Semi professional	3	0	1	5			
c. Daily wage worker	4	1	0	4			
d. Self employed	0	1	0	5			
e. Housewife	9	4	6	39			
6. Monthly family income							
a. Less than 15,000	9	5	3	34	16.47	9	0.058 ^{NS}
b. 16,000-45,000	7	1	2	15			
c. 46,000-75,000	0	0	1	7			
d. More than 75,000	0	0	1	0			
7. Type of family							
a. Joint family	10	2	3	24	3.772	7	0.708 ^{NS}
b. Nuclear family	6	4	4	29			
c. Single parent	0	0	0	3			
8. Support person available							
a. Yes	9	4	5	35	0.548	3	0.908 ^{NS}
b. No	7	2	2	21			
9. Residency							
a. Urban	2	1	2	19	3.248	3	0.355 ^{NS}
b. Rural	14	5	5	37			
10. Duration of pregnancy							
a. 8 months	1	1	0	5	1.312	3	0.726 ^{NS}
b. 9 months	15	5	7	51			
11. ANC follow up till date							
a. Only one time	1	0	0	4	5.362	9	0.802 ^{NS}
b. Twice	0	1	0	4			
c. Three times	2	1	2	6			
d. More than 3 times	13	4	5	42			
12. Antenatal counseling received							
a. Yes	7	3	3	22	0.327	3	0.955 ^{NS}
b. No	9	3	4	34			
13. Any health education regarding new-born feeding?							
a. Yes	6	3	2	21	0.636	3	0.888 ^{NS}
b. No	10	3	5	35			

The result depicts that there was no association.

Table 7. Association between what kind of Prelacteal feed was administered to the new-born among immediate postnatal mothers with selected demographic variables

Demographic Variables	what kind of prelacteal feed was administered				z ² value	df	p value
	Honey	Ghee	Water	NAN			
1. Age in years							
a. Less than 20 years	2	0	1	3	18.62	9	0.029*
b. 21-25 years	6	2	1	16			
c. 26-30 years	5	15	3	21			
d. More than 31 years	5	0	0	5			
2. Religion					7.376	9	0.598 ^{NS}
a. Hindu	10	6	2	22			
b. Buddhist	5	6	3	16			
c. Muslim	--	--	--	--			
d. Christian	3	4	0	7			
e. Others	0	1	0	0			
3. Educational status					15.49	12	0.216 ^{NS}
a. No formal education	4	1	0	5			
b. Primary	7	3	3	12			
c. Secondary	6	9	0	18			
d. Graduate	0	3	1	9			
e. Postgraduate	1	1	1	1			
f. PhD	--	--	--	--			
4. Husbands Educational status					17.61	12	0.128 ^{NS}
a. No formal education	3	0	1	2			
b. Primary	8	7	18	4			
c. Secondary	5	9	20	4			
d. Graduate	2	1	5	6			
e. Postgraduate	0	0	1	2			
f. PhD	--	--	--	--			
5. Occupational status					10.06	12	0.611 ^{NS}
a. Professional	0	1	0	2			
b. Semi professional	1	3	1	4			
c. Daily wage worker	3	2	0	4			
d. Self employed	0	0	0	6			
e. Housewife	14	11	4	29			
6. Monthly family income					26.31	9	0.002*
a. Less than 15,000	15	9	3	24			
b. 16,000-45,000	2	8	1	14			
c. 46,000-75,000	1	0	0	7			
d. More than 75,000	0	0	1	0			
7. Type of family					7.187	6	0.304 ^{NS}
a. Joint family	9	10	1	19			
b. Nuclear family	9	7	3	24			
c. Single parent	0	0	1	2			
8. Support person available					1.200	3	0.753 ^{NS}
a. Yes	11	11	2	29			
b. No	7	6	3	16			
9. Residency					5.251	3	0.154 ^{NS}
a. Urban	4	3	0	17			
b. Rural	14	14	5	28			
10. Duration of pregnancy					2.837	3	0.417 ^{NS}
a. 8 month	0	2	1	4			
b. 9 month	18	15	4	41			
11. ANC follow up till date					6.649	9	0.674 ^{NS}
a. Only one time	1	0	1	3			
b. Twice	1	2	0	2			
c. Three times	4	2	1	4			
d. More than 3 times	12	13	3	36			
12. Antenatal counseling received					4.026	3	0.259 ^{NS}
a. Yes	6	8	4	17			
b. No	12	9	1	28			
13. Any health education regarding new-born feeding?					1.200	3	0.753 ^{NS}
a. Yes	7	6	3	16			
b. No	11	11	2	29			

Table 7 depicts that age and monthly income was found to have significant association at p<0.05 level with Prelacteal feed administered to new-born among immediate postnatal mothers .

Table 8: Association between factor influencing Prelacteal feeding among immediate postnatal mothers with selected demographic variables

Demographic Variables	Factor influencing prelacteal feed					χ ² value	df	p value
	Cultural Belief	Advice from peer	Advice from religious head	Good health of baby	Others			
1. Age in years								
a. Less than 20 years	1	0	2	0	3	15.10	12	0.236 ^{NS}
b. 21-25 years	3	2	1	4	15			
c. 26-30 years	11	0	9	3	22			
d. More than 31 years	3	0	2	0	5			
2. Religion								
a. Hindu	9	2	6	2	21	11.66	12	0.473 ^{NS}
b. Buddhist	6	0	6	1	17			
c. Muslim	--	--	--	--	--			
d. Christian	2	0	2	3	7			
e. Others	1	0	0	0	0			
3. Educational status								
a. No formal education	4	0	1	0	5	14.10	16	0.591 ^{NS}
b. Primary	5	0	5	3	12			
c. Secondary	5	2	6	2	18			
d. Graduate	2	0	2	0	9			
e. Postgraduate	2	0	0	1	1			
f. PhD	--	--	--	--	--			
4. Husbands Educational status								
a. No formal education	1	0	2	1	1	11.76	16	0.760 ^{NS}
b. Primary	9	0	5	2	18			
c. Secondary	6	1	6	3	20			
d. Graduate	1	1	1	0	5			
e. Postgraduate	1	0	0	0	1			
f. PhD	--	--	--	--	--			
5. Occupational status								
a. Professional	1	0	0	0	2	13.49	16	0.636 ^{NS}
b. Semi professional	1	0	2	2	4			
c. Daily wage worker	2	0	3	0	4			
d. Self employed	0	0	0	0	6			
e. Housewife	14	2	9	4	29			
6. Monthly family income								
a. Less than 15,000	14	1	8	3	25	9.548	12	0.656 ^{NS}
b. 16,000-45,000	3	1	5	2	14			
c. 46,000-75,000	0	0	1	1	6			
d. More than 75,000	1	0	0	0	0			
7. Type of family								
a. Joint family	8	1	7	4	19	2.279	8	0.971 ^{NS}
b. Nuclear family	9	1	7	2	24			
c. Single parent	1	0	0	0	2			
8. Support person available								
a. Yes	13	1	7	3	29	2.261	4	0.688 ^{NS}
b. No	5	1	7	3	16			
9. Residency								
a. Urban	2	1	3	1	17	5.811	4	0.214 ^{NS}
b. Rural	16	1	11	5	28			
10. Duration of pregnancy								
a. 8 months	2	0	1	0	4	0.962	4	0.915 ^{NS}
b. 9 months	16	2	13	6	41			
11. ANC follow up till date								
a. Only one time	2	0	0	0	3	7.106	12	0.851 ^{NS}
b. Twice	1	0	2	0	2			
c. Three times	3	0	3	1	4			
d. More than 3 times	12	2	9	5	36			
12. Antenatal counseling received								
a. Yes	8	1	7	3	16	1.373	4	0.849 ^{NS}
b. No	10	1	7	3	29			
13. Any health education regarding new-born feeding?								
a. Yes	7	1	6	2	16	0.435	4	0.979 ^{NS}
b. No	11	1	8	4	29			

*p value < 0.05 level of significance NS-Non-Significant

Table 8 depicts that there is no association.

Conclusion

Introduction of Prelacteal feeds is a known barrier to continuation of exclusive breastfeeding. These practices vary by country and may include throwing away colostrum – a mother’s “first milk” rich in antibodies – or having a doctor or elder family member give the new-born specific liquids or foods, like formula, sugar water or honey. These practices can delay a baby’s first critical contact with his or her mother.

The present study revealed that despite having good knowledge, 29% of the total sample still practicing prelacteal feeding which was influenced by the cultural factor as well as other reasons like baby being admitted to NICU, no milk secretion etc.

Thus, the health care workers can directly influence such practices by providing adequate health education on breastfeeding and harmful effect of such practices by minimising the usage of formula feed and other breastmilk substitutes in NICU as well as in postnatal ward.

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